

Supplementary Material: Efficient and faithful reconstruction of dynamical attractors using homogeneous differentiators

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Abstract

Here we provide Supplementary Material for our work on the efficient and faithful reconstruction of dynamical attractors using Homogeneous Differentiators. In particular,

- in Section S1, we thoroughly review the theory of Homogeneous Differentiators;
- we provide further details about the considered nonlinear dynamical models (Lorenz chaotic system in Section S2, Hindmarsh-Rose model in Section S3, Epileptor model in Section S4), their analysis and the obtained attractor reconstruction results;
- in Section S5, we provide additional information about attractor reconstruction from empirical time series data obtained from measurements of the brain activity of Zebrafish larvae.

S1 Homogeneous filtering Differentiators

We supplement Section 2 in the Main Manuscript by providing additional details and a thorough overview of the theory of Homogeneous Differentiators. Throughout this section, given any $x \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}_+$, we denote $[x]^\alpha := |x|^\alpha \text{sign}(x)$, where, for $x \in \mathbb{R}$,

$$\text{sign}(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & x > 0, \\ 0, & x = 0, \\ -1, & x < 0. \end{cases}$$

We further assume that Assumptions 1 and 2 in Section 2.1 of the Main Manuscript hold for the continuous-time Homogeneous Differentiator, whereas Assumptions 1 and 3 in Section 2.1 of the Main Manuscript hold for the discrete-time homogeneous differentiator. To further clarify the class of admissible noises, we recall the following definitions from [1].

Definition 1. A function $v: \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a (globally filterable) signal of the global filtering order $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$ if (i) v is a locally integrable Lebesgue-measurable function and (ii) there exists a globally bounded solution $\xi(t)$ to the equation $\xi^{(k)}(t) = v(t)$. Globally filterable signals of order 0 are measurable and essentially bounded functions. The value $\sup_{t \in \mathbb{R}_+} |\xi(t)|$ is the k -th order global integral magnitude of $v(t)$.

Definition 2. A locally integrable Lebesgue-measurable function $v: \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a (locally filterable) signal of the local filtering order $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$ if there exist numbers $T > 0, a_0, \dots, a_{k-1} \geq 0$ such that, for any $t_1 \in \mathbb{R}_+$,

- there exists a solution $\xi(t)$ on $[t_1, t_1 + T]$ to the ordinary differential equation $\xi^{(k)}(t) = v(t)$;
- the solution $\xi(t)$ satisfies $|\xi^{(\ell)}(t)| \leq a_\ell$ for $\ell = 0, \dots, k - 1$.

Signals of the local filtering order 0 are defined as essentially bounded signals of magnitude a_0 .

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Definitions 1 and 2 describe a broad class of admissible noises for which homogeneous differentiators possess rigorous differentiation error estimates (see below). Intuitively speaking, a noise $\eta(t)$ that is globally filterable of order $k \in \mathbb{N}$ is such that integrating it k times produces a *globally* bounded signal $\xi(t)$. Such a noise $\eta(t)$ may be unbounded and/or oscillatory; however, integration leads to cancellations that yield as a result a bounded signal $\xi(t)$.

An example of a globally filterable noise of order 1 is given by $\eta(t) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{t}}e^{-t} - \sqrt{t}e^{-t}$, $t \in (0, \infty)$ and $\eta(0) = 0$. Clearly, $\eta(t)$ is unbounded in a right neighbourhood of $t = 0$. However, integrating $\eta(t)$ gives $\int_0^t \eta(s)ds = \sqrt{t}e^{-t}$, which is globally bounded.

Definition 2 extends Definition 1 by including noise terms $\eta(t)$ that, after being integrated k times, yield only a *locally* bounded solution $\xi(t)$.

A locally filterable noise of order 1 is, for instance, $\eta(t) = \cos(30t \ln(\ln(t+2)))$; see [1, Example 2].

In the context of homogeneous differentiators, developing error bounds for the case of globally filterable noises immediately covers also the case of locally filterable ones, since any locally filterable noise can be decomposed into a sum of globally filterable ones: this is guaranteed by [1, Lemma 1], reported next.

Lemma 1. *Any noise $\eta(t)$ of the local filtering order $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$ can be decomposed as the sum $\eta(t) = \eta_0(t) + \eta_1(t) + \dots + \eta_k(t)$, where $\eta_j(t)$ is a noise of the global filtering order j for $j \in \{0, 1, k\}$.*

Hence, in what follows, we limit ourselves to only stating results that involve globally filterable noises.

S1.1 Continuous-time Homogeneous filtering Differentiators

Let now $f(t) = f_0(t) + \eta(t)$, $t \in \mathbb{R}_+$ be a measured signal with (clean) base signal $f_0(t)$ and noise $\eta(t)$ satisfying Assumptions 1 and 2 from Section 2.1 in the Main Manuscript, respectively. Given the parameters n_d , n_f and L_0 , the equations of the continuous-time homogeneous filtering differentiator are given by

$$\begin{cases} \dot{w}_1 = -\tilde{\lambda}_{n_d+n_f} L_0^{\frac{1}{n_d+n_f+1}} [w_1]^{\frac{n_d+n_f}{n_d+n_f+1}} + w_2, \\ \vdots \\ \dot{w}_{n_f-1} = -\tilde{\lambda}_{n_d+2} L_0^{\frac{n_f-1}{n_d+n_f+1}} [w_1]^{\frac{n_d+2}{n_d+n_f+1}} + w_{n_f}, \\ \dot{w}_{n_f} = -\tilde{\lambda}_{n_d+1} L_0^{\frac{n_f}{n_d+n_f+1}} [w_1]^{\frac{n_d+1}{n_d+n_f+1}} + z_0 - f(t), \\ \dot{z}_0 = -\tilde{\lambda}_{n_d} L_0^{\frac{n_f+1}{n_d+n_f+1}} [w_1]^{\frac{n_d}{n_d+n_f+1}} + z_1, \\ \vdots \\ \dot{z}_{n_d-1} = -\tilde{\lambda}_1 L_0^{\frac{n_d+n_f}{n_d+n_f+1}} [w_1]^{\frac{1}{n_d+n_f+1}} + z_{n_d}, \\ \dot{z}_n = -\tilde{\lambda}_0 L_0 \text{sign}(w_1), \end{cases} \quad \text{for } n_f > 0, \quad \text{while } w_1 = z_0 - f \text{ for } n_f = 0,$$

which is compactly written (as reported in Eq. (1) of the Main Manuscript) as

$$\begin{cases} w_1 = z_0 - f, & \text{for } n_f = 0, \\ \dot{w} = \Omega_{n_d, n_f}(w, z_0 - f, L_0, \lambda), & \text{for } n_f > 0, \end{cases} \quad \text{and} \quad \dot{z} = D_{n_d, n_f}(w_1, z, L_0, \lambda), \quad (\text{S1})$$

where parameters $\lambda = (\tilde{\lambda}_0, \dots, \tilde{\lambda}_{n_d+n_f})$ exist for any $n_d + n_f \in \mathbb{N}_0$, as discussed in [2, 3], and can be obtained via a recursive computation; typical values are reported in [3, Figure 1]. For example, for $n_d + n_f = 6$, λ is given by (1.1, 9.91, 43.65, 101.96, 110.08, 47.69, 10). In this work, the values of λ are chosen according to [3, Figure 1].

The homogeneous differentiator possesses rigorous theoretical guarantees on the errors between the differentiator output and the derivatives of the base signal $f_0(t)$. These are provided in [1, Theorem 2], which we rephrase below.

Theorem 1. *Let Assumptions 1 and 2 in Section 2.1 of the Main Manuscript hold. Assume that the noise $\eta(t)$ is decomposed as $\eta(t) = \sum_{j=0}^{n_f} \eta_j(t)$, where $\eta_j(t)$ is globally filterable of order j and has global integral magnitude $\epsilon_j \geq 0$ for $j \in \{0, \dots, k\}$. Then, the homogeneous differentiator (S1) provides the following accuracy, in finite time:*

$$\begin{aligned} |z_i(t) - f_0^{(i)}(t)| &\leq \mu_i L_0 \rho^{n_d+1-i}, \quad i = 0, \dots, n_d, \\ |w_1(t)| &\leq \mu_{w_1} L_0 \rho^{n_d+n_f+1}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\rho = \max_{0 \leq j \leq n_f} \left\{ \left(\frac{\epsilon_j}{L_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{n_d+j+1}} \right\}$$

and μ_{w_1} and μ_i , $i = 0, \dots, n_d$, are positive constants that depend only on λ .

In the absence of the noise $\eta(t)$, Theorem 1 guarantees perfect recovery of $f_0(t)$ in finite time. Moreover, assuming that $\max_i \epsilon_i < L_0$, we have that $\rho < 1$ in Theorem 1. Then, up to the multiplicative constants μ_i , $i = 0, \dots, n_d$, Theorem 1 implies that reconstructing higher derivatives of $f_0(t)$ comes at the cost of larger error bounds. This is to be expected from the inherent ill-posedness of differentiation, which causes the errors to grow with the order of the derivative. Assuming further that $\epsilon_i = \epsilon$ for all $i = 0, \dots, n_d$ and $n_f = 0$, the differentiation error in Theorem 1 becomes

$$\left| z_i(t) - f_0^{(i)}(t) \right| \leq \mu_i L_0 \left(\frac{\epsilon}{L_0} \right)^{\frac{n_d+1-i}{n_d+1}}, \quad i = 0, \dots, n_d,$$

which implies that homogeneous differentiators achieve, up to multiplicative constants, the best possible differentiation error, as a function of ϵ . This is a corollary of the following result in [4, Proposition 1].

Theorem 2. *For any $t_0 > 0$, there exists $\epsilon_*(t_0) > 0$ such that, for any $0 < \epsilon \leq \epsilon_*(t_0)$ and any two functions f_0 and f_1 that are $n_d + 1$ times continuously differentiable and satisfy $\left| f_0^{(n_d+1)}(t) \right| \leq L_0$ and $\left| f_1^{(n_d+1)}(t) \right| \leq L_0$ for all $t \geq 0$, the inequality $\sup_{t \geq 0} |f_0(t) - f_1(t)| \leq \epsilon$ implies that*

$$\sup_{t \geq t_0} \left| f_0^{(i)}(t) - f_1^{(i)}(t) \right| \leq K_{i,n_d} (2L_0)^{\frac{i}{n_d+1}} \epsilon^{\frac{n_d+1-i}{n_d+1}}, \quad i = 0, \dots, n_d,$$

where K_{i,n_d} are (Kolmogorov) constants. Furthermore, for each ϵ and $i = 0, \dots, n_d$, these inequalities become equalities for some functions $f_0(t)$ and $f_1(t)$.

Theorem 2 implies that the differentiation errors obtained in Theorem 1 are, in general, the best possible. We give an intuitive explanation here; for a more rigorous discussion, see [4]. Denote by $\text{Lip}_{n_d}(L_0)$ the class of functions $h(t)$ that are $n_d + 1$ times continuously differentiable and satisfy $\left| h^{(n_d+1)}(t) \right| \leq L_0$ for all $t \in \mathbb{R}_+$. Assume that we are given an ideal differentiator algorithm \mathfrak{D} , producing outputs $\hat{z}_0(t), \dots, \hat{z}_{n_d}(t)$: for any $h \in \text{Lip}_{n_d}(L_0)$, \mathfrak{D} yields $\hat{z}_i(t) = h^{(i)}(t)$ after some finite time $T \in \mathbb{R}_+$, which may depend on h . This assumption means that \mathfrak{D} is able to recover functions in $\text{Lip}_{n_d}(L_0)$ and their derivatives up to n_d exactly in the *absence* of noise, and constitutes a reasonable requirement from a viable differentiation algorithm. Consider arbitrary $t_0 > 0$, $0 < \epsilon \leq \epsilon_*(t_0)$ and $f_0, f_1 \in \text{Lip}_{n_d}(L_0)$ for which we have equality in Theorem 2 with $i = 1$. Assume that we employ \mathfrak{D} to recover f_0 , but the noise $\eta(t)$ is chosen in an adversarial fashion as $\eta(t) = f_1(t) - f_0(t)$ with $|\eta(t)| \leq \epsilon$, $t \in \mathbb{R}_+$, meaning that we measure $f_1(t)$ instead of $f_0(t)$. Since $f_1 \in \text{Lip}_{n_d}(L_0)$, \mathfrak{D} is exact on f_1 and

$$\sup_{t \geq t_0} \left| \hat{z}_1(t) - f_0^{(1)}(t) \right| = K_{1,n_d} (2L_0)^{\frac{1}{n_d+1}} \epsilon^{\frac{n_d}{n_d+1}}.$$

Thus, the output \hat{z}_1 of \mathfrak{D} has a supremum error proportional to $\epsilon^{\frac{n_d}{n_d+1}}$ on the interval $[t_0, \infty)$. Since t_0 is arbitrary, the differentiation error of \mathfrak{D} in the output $\hat{z}_1(t)$ cannot scale better than $\epsilon^{\frac{n_d}{n_d+1}}$ in the noise magnitude ϵ . Recalling Theorem 1, this is exactly the same scaling in ϵ that is obtained by the homogeneous differentiator. Similar arguments hold for estimation of higher-order derivatives.

S1.2 Discrete-time Homogeneous filtering Differentiators

To use the homogeneous differentiator (S1) in applications, it is necessary to appropriately discretise (S1), in order to allow for digital implementation that only uses a sampled time-series of the signal $f(t)$. Such a discretisation requires the choice of sampling step size bounds $0 < \underline{\theta} \leq \bar{\theta}$. Then, a discrete sequence of sampling times $\{t_s\}_{s=1}^{\infty}$ is chosen to satisfy $\underline{\theta} \leq t_{s+1} - t_s = \theta_s \leq \bar{\theta}$, which guarantees $\lim_{s \rightarrow \infty} t_s = \infty$.

In order to obtain provable theoretical guarantees on the performance of discrete-time homogeneous differentiators, Definitions 1 and 2 are replaced by the following definitions from [1].

Definition 3. *A discretely sampled signal $v: \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a signal of the global sampling filtering order $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and the global k -th order integral sampling magnitude $a \in \mathbb{R}_+$ if, for each admissible sequence $\{t_s\}_{s=1}^{\infty}$ with $t_{s+1} - t_s = \theta_s$, there exists a discrete vector signal $\xi(t_s) = (\xi_0(t_s), \dots, \xi_k(t_s))^{\top} \in \mathbb{R}^{k+1}$ that satisfies the relations*

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_i(t_{s+1}) &= \xi_i(t_s) + \xi_{i+1}(t_s)\theta_s, \quad i = 0, \dots, k-1, \\ \xi_k(t_s) &= v(t_s), \\ \left| \xi_0(t_s) \right| &\leq a \end{aligned}$$

for all $s \in \mathbb{N}$.

Definition 4. *A discretely sampled signal $v: \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a signal of the local sampling filtering order $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$ if there exist numbers $T > 0$ and $a_0, \dots, a_{k-1} \geq 0$ such that, for any sufficiently small $\bar{\theta} > 0$, any admissible sequence $\{t_s\}_{s=1}^{\infty}$ with $t_{s+1} - t_s = \theta_s \leq \bar{\theta}$, and any $t_{s_0} \geq 0$, there exists a discrete vector signal $\xi(t_s) = (\xi_0(t_s), \dots, \xi_k(t_s))^{\top} \in \mathbb{R}^{k+1}$ and indices $s = s_0, s_0 + 1, \dots, s_1$ with $t_{s_1} \in [t_{s_0} + T, t_{s_0} + T + \bar{\theta}]$ and $t_{s_1+1} \geq t_{s_0} + T + \bar{\theta}$, that satisfies the relations*

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_i(t_{s+1}) &= \xi_i(t_s) + \xi_{i+1}(t_s)\theta_s, \quad i = 0, \dots, k-1, \\ \xi_k(t_s) &= v(t_s), \\ \left| \xi_i(t_s) \right| &\leq a_i, \quad i = 0, \dots, k-1, \end{aligned}$$

for all $s \in \mathbb{N}$. Signals of the local sampling filtering order 0 are bounded signals of magnitude a_0 .

Definitions 3 and 4 are the discrete-time analogues of Definitions 1 and 2, respectively: the finite-difference scheme given in both Definitions 3 and 4 is a discrete-time analogue of the continuous-time chain of integrators in Definitions 1 and 2. Recalling Lemma 1, it is not surprising that the result in [1, Lemma 2], reported below, holds for the decomposition of a noise of the local sampling filtering order k into a sum of noises of a global sampling filtering order.

Lemma 2. *Any discretely sampled noise $\eta(t_s)$ of the local sampling filtering order $k \in \mathbb{N}_0$ can be decomposed as $\eta(t_s) = \eta_0(t_s) + \eta_1(t_s) + \eta_k(t_s)$, where η_j is a discretely sampled noise of the global sampling filtering order j for $j \in \{0, 1, k\}$.*

The discretisation of (S1) takes the form of the finite-difference scheme

$$\begin{aligned} w(t_{s+1}) &= w(t_s) + \Omega_{n_d, n_f}(w(t_s), z_0(t_s) - f(t_s), L_0, \lambda)\theta_s, \\ z(t_{s+1}) &= z(t_s) + D_{n_d, n_f}(w_1(t_s), z(t_s), L_0, \lambda)\theta_s + T_{n_d}(z(t_s), \theta_s), \end{aligned} \tag{S2}$$

where $T_{n_d}(z(t_s), \theta_s) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_d}$ for all $s \in \mathbb{N}$ has components

$$\begin{aligned} T_{n_d,0} &= \frac{1}{2!} z_2(t_s) \theta_s^2 + \cdots + \frac{1}{n_d!} z_{n_d}(t_s) \theta_s^{n_d}, \\ T_{n_d,1} &= \frac{1}{2!} z_3(t_s) \theta_s^2 + \cdots + \frac{1}{(n_d-1)!} z_{n_d}(t_s) \theta_s^{n_d-1}, \\ &\vdots \\ T_{n_d,n_d-2} &= \frac{1}{2!} z_{n_d}(t_s) \theta_s^2, \\ T_{n_d,n_d-1} &= 0, \quad T_{n_d,n_d} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Here, $T_{n_d}(z(t_s), \theta_s)$ is a Taylor-like correction term, which is introduced to preserve the accuracy of the continuous-time scheme after discretisation. Differently from the case of the continuous-time HD, the differentiation error bounds for the discrete-time HD depend linearly also on the step-size bound $\bar{\theta}$, which should be chosen so as to allow for the desired differentiator accuracy. In fact, the following error bounds hold for homogeneous discrete-time differentiators, as proven in [1, Theorem 5].

Theorem 3. *Let Assumptions 1 and 3 in Section 2.1 of the Main Manuscript hold. Then, the discrete-time homogeneous differentiator provides the following accuracy, in finite time:*

$$\begin{aligned} |z_i(t) - f_0^{(i)}(t)| &\leq \mu_i L_0 \rho^{n_d+1-i}, \quad i = 0, \dots, n_d, \\ |w_1(t)| &\leq \mu_{w_1} L_0 \rho^{n_d+n_f+1}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\rho = \max \left[\bar{\theta}, \max_{0 \leq s \leq n_f} \left(\frac{\bar{\epsilon}_s}{L_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{n_d+s+1}}, \max_{1 \leq s \leq n_f} \max_{1 \leq q \leq s} \left(\frac{L_{\eta_s}}{L_0} \left(\frac{\bar{\epsilon}_s}{L_{\eta_s}} \right)^{\frac{q+1}{s+1}} \right)^{\frac{1}{n_d+q+1}} \right]$$

and $\mu_{w_1}, \mu_i, i = 0, \dots, n_d$ are positive constants that depend only on λ .

A common drawback of the discrete-time homogeneous differentiator (S2) lies in the effect that choosing a large upper bound L_0 for the magnitude of $|f_0^{n_d+1}(t)|$, $t \in \mathbb{R}_+$, has on the HD output. The actual value $\sup_{t \in \mathbb{R}_+} |f_0^{n_d+1}(t)| =: L$ is never available in practice. Hence, the discrete-time homogeneous differentiator (S2) employs an a-priori upper bound L_0 , aimed to satisfy $L \leq L_0$. However, choosing L_0 much larger than L may lead to the output exhibiting slow convergence from large initial errors, as well as chattering (i.e., high-frequency small oscillations), both of which are undesirable phenomena.

Discrete L-adaptation To mitigate these effects when the bound L_0 is possibly much larger than L , in this work we employ a modification of the discrete-time homogeneous differentiator (S2), called *discrete L-adaptation* [3]. The idea behind this modification is to replace L_0 in the discrete-time homogeneous differentiator (S2) by an adaptive sequence $L(t_s)$ in order to achieve better performance of the differentiator when L_0 is much larger than L , while maintaining the accuracy reported in Theorem 3. In particular, this is achieved by introducing parameters $k_{\bar{\theta}} > 0$ and $q \geq -\frac{1}{n_d+n_f+1}$ and replacing L_0 in (S2) by

$$L(t_s) = L_0 \text{sat} \left(\frac{|w_1(t_s)|}{L_0 w_{\bar{\theta}}} \right)^{1+(n_d+n_f+1)q}, \quad w_{\bar{\theta}} = k_{\bar{\theta}} \bar{\theta}^{n_d+n_f+1},$$

where $\text{sat}(\zeta) = \max(-1, \min(1, \zeta))$, $\zeta \in \mathbb{R}$. In this work, we apply the discrete L-adaptation in [3] with $q = 0$ and values of $k_{\bar{\theta}}$ selected according to [3, Table I], which are valid for our choice of λ according to [3, Figure 1], as discussed in Section S1.1.

S2 Lorenz system

The Lorenz'63 system [5] is given by

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_1(t) = \sigma[x_2(t) - x_1(t)] \\ \dot{x}_2(t) = rx_1(t) - x_2(t) - x_1(t)x_3(t) \\ \dot{x}_3(t) = x_1(t)x_2(t) - bx_3(t) \end{cases} \quad (\text{S3})$$

with state vector $x(t) = [x_1(t) \ x_2(t) \ x_3(t)]^\top$; the parameter values can be set as $\sigma = 10$, $b = 8/3$ and $r = 28$ to obtain a chaotic attractor. We simulate the system trajectory emanating from the initial condition $x(0) = [1 \ 1 \ 1]^\top$, then a transient of 1,000 time units is removed from a total simulation time of 1,020 time units so as to let the trajectory converge to its attractor. The simulation encompasses 10,000 time points per time unit, which means that after discarding the transient we have a total of 200,001 time points. We measure the clean (base) signal $\bar{y}(t) = x_1(t)$. Measurement noise $\eta(t)$ is introduced at each time step, as described in the Main Manuscript: the five noise types described in Section 2.4 of the Main Manuscript are injected so as to affect the measured signal both in an additive ($y(t) = \bar{y}(t) + \eta(t)$) and in a multiplicative ($y(t) = [1 + \eta(t)]\bar{y}(t)$) fashion, thus yielding the ten different noisy signals shown in Figure S1. We first apply the Differentiator and then we remove the data corresponding to the first unit of time in order to obtain an output that does not contain the finite-time transient of the Differentiator [1]; see also Section S1.

S2.1 Processing

From simulated noisy time series, we wish to reconstruct the attractor in the $\{x_1, x_2\}$ sub-space, which is fully observable [6, Section IV.A]. The true noise-free attractor, to which we can compare our reconstruction, is known from the time evolution of the two variables.

Our processing steps are visualised in Figure S2. We have access to noisy measurements y of x_1 , corresponding to the time series depicted in Figure S1, to which we apply the Differentiator so as to obtain de-noised estimates of the signal y , which is an approximation of x_1 , and of its derivative \dot{y} , which is an approximation of \dot{x}_1 . Then, from the first equation in system (S3), we can approximate $x_2 = \frac{\dot{x}_1}{\sigma} + x_1$ as $\frac{\dot{y}}{\sigma} + y$. The resulting differential embedding allows us to reconstruct the attractor in the original state-space coordinates x_1 and x_2 , as sketched in Figure S2.

As discussed in Section S1, the Differentiator has three parameters (see Figure S2, as well as Figure 1 in the Main Manuscript): n_d , n_f and L_0 . We set $n_d = 2$ and $n_f = 3$, see [1], which results in $\lambda = (1.1, 6.75, 20.26, 32.24, 23.72, 7)$ as per [3, Figure 1]. Moreover, L_0 is chosen iteratively through a post-hoc analysis procedure, looking for the minimum value of L_0 that yields an exact overlapping between the signal and its derivative generated by the Differentiator in the absence of noise, and the true original signals (see Figure S3): we obtain $L_0 = 3.75 \cdot 10^4$. Determining effective heuristics to set L_0 a priori is a challenging avenue for future work.

Moreover, to implement the discrete L -adaptation of the Differentiator, we consider parameters $q = 0$, as well as $k_{\bar{p}} = 400$ corresponding to the chosen λ as per [3, Table I].

We also consider a 2D time-delay embedding of the measured time series y de-noised by the Differentiator, so as to be able to compare the results with direct embedding of the noisy measurements, and with its de-noised version through the Schreiber-Grassberger algorithm [7, 8]. The embedding delay is chosen consistently with guidelines from the literature [9]: we use a custom code to compute a time delay that results in maximally distant trajectories in the time-delay coordinates space. In this particular case, since the Lorenz system is well known, we pick a priori the widely used value $\tau = 0.1$. The dimension of the original attractor is known, since we know the system; we choose $\ell = 1$ to have a 2D embedding for ease of visualisation.

Since the Differentiator outputs may suffer from chattering [3], in our numerical tests we compare the results obtained by using them directly with those obtained by additionally processing the Differentiator

Figure S1: **Clean and noisy signals considered for the Lorenz system.** Time series of the clean (base) measured signal $\bar{y} = x_1$ for the Lorenz system (S3), in black, affected by additive (left) and multiplicative (right) noise to yield the measured signal y , in colour. From top to bottom, Gaussian noise $\eta_1(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.01)$ (blue), $\eta_2(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.1)$ (orange), $\eta_3(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ (violet); harmonic noise $\eta_H(t)$ as in Eq. (5) of the Main Manuscript (green); unbounded noise $\eta_U(t)$ as in Eq. (6) of the Main Manuscript (red). See Section 2.4 of the Main Manuscript for details about the different noise types.

Figure S2: **Block diagram of the attractor reconstruction procedure for the Lorenz system (S3) based on the Differentiator outputs.** The clean (base) measured signal $\bar{y} = x_1$ corrupted by the noise η yields the (noisy) measured signal y , which is then processed by the Differentiator to generate a de-noised estimate of y , y_D , and of its derivative, \dot{y}_D . Approximating x_1 as y_D and x_2 as $\frac{\dot{y}_D}{\sigma} + y_D$ allows reconstruction of the system attractor in the original state-space coordinates x_1 and x_2 .

outputs with a Savitzky-Golay (SG) filter [10], so as to make the signals smoother without distorting their features. For the SG filter, we choose a second-order polynomial for the local least-squares approximation and we use different widths of the approximation interval M depending on the type of measurement noise (see [10] for details). The output reconstruction, for the different noise types, is shown in Figure S4.

Figure S3: **Iterative procedure to choose the Differentiator parameter L_0 .** We show time series of the clean (base) measured signal $\bar{y} = x_1$ for the Lorenz system (S3) and of its derivative $\dot{\bar{y}} = \dot{x}_1$, in blue, along with the corresponding signals y_D and \dot{y}_D reconstructed by the Differentiator with $n_d = 2$, in red, for different values of L_0 . To account for the effect of L_0 only, we carry out the procedure with filtration degree $n_f = 0$ and in the absence of noise, $\eta \equiv 0$.

Figure S4: **Differentiator output for the Lorenz system: de-noised estimate of the measured signal and of its time derivative.** Time series of the clean (base) measured signal $\bar{y} = x_1$ for the Lorenz system (S3) and of its derivative $\dot{\bar{y}} = \dot{x}_1$, in blue, along with the corresponding signals y_D and \dot{y}_D , in red, reconstructed by the Differentiator with parameters $n_d = 2$, $n_f = 3$, $L_0 = 3.75 \cdot 10^4$, $q = 0$, $k_{\bar{\theta}} = 400$, in the presence of additive (left) and multiplicative (right) noise η_i , $i \in \{1, 2, 3, U, H\}$, as in Figure S1.

S2.2 Distribution of errors

To comparatively assess the quality of attractor reconstruction using different methods, we compute the relative reconstruction error $E_R(k)$, given by Eq. (3) in the Main Manuscript, between corresponding points of the true attractor in the time-delay embedding space and of the reconstructed attractor in the same space. The error value $E_R(k)$ is computed for each data point k ; hence, a distribution of errors can be constructed. Figure S5 shows the error distributions for the whole attractor (the summary statistics are reported in Table 1 of the Main Manuscript) for the different noise types η_i , $i \in \{1, 2, 3, U, H\}$, both in the case in which they corrupt the data additively and in the case in which they corrupt the data multiplicatively. We compare different noise reduction methods: the Differentiator, the Differentiator with post-filtering using the Savitzky-Golay (SG) filter, and the Schreiber-Grassberger de-noising method.

Due to the long computation times required by the Schreiber-Grassberger method, we perform the analysis only once even for stochastic noise; in any case, the differences between the methods are so large that the order of magnitude remains unchanged regardless of the exact noise values. To ensure reproducibility, the code includes an initial seed.

Note that, according to [8], the Schreiber-Grassberger method may be run more than once, to possibly improve the reconstruction. For all the tested systems, running the method twice subsequently did not provide any significant improvement, while it increased the computation time by additional 7 to 8 hours at least. Hence, the Schreiber-Grassberger method was applied only once in all the analysis results shown here.

Figure S5: **Lorenz system: the distribution of reconstruction errors, along with average, median and worst-case errors, shows the considerable improvement in faithfulness achieved by the Differentiator-based attractor reconstruction.** Distribution of the relative reconstruction errors $E_R(k)$, see Eq. (3) in the Main Manuscript, for the reconstruction of the attractor of the Lorenz system (S3), for all the considered noise types, both additive and multiplicative, and for the different noise reduction methods: Differentiator (blue), Differentiator with SG post-filtering (green, with parameter M tuned for each noise type to minimise chattering, reported on the left), Schreiber-Grassberger method (orange). The Differentiator parameters are as in Figure S4.

S2.3 Space-filling: holes

In addition to considering the relative error, we can assess the quality in reconstructing the attractor by quantifying how faithfully some key topological properties are preserved. In particular, we focus on the space-filling property of the trajectories, as discussed in Section 2.3 of the Main Manuscript.

To do so, we employ a methodology based on the box counting approach [11]. First, we consider a region of interest: if we are interested in evaluating the global space-filling characteristic of the reconstructed attractor, the region corresponds to the box containing all the data points $\bar{\mathbf{y}}(k) = [\bar{y}(k) \ \bar{y}(k + \frac{\tau}{\Delta t}) \ \dots \ \bar{y}(k + \ell \frac{\tau}{\Delta t})]^\top$. Then, we partition this region into sub-boxes of bin width b_w , and we compute the number of sub-boxes that contain at least one point of the considered time series (after a transient, so that the trajectories have converged to the attractor) as a function of the bin width b_w , for smaller and smaller values of b_w .

For computational reasons, we stop at a minimum bin width $b_w = 0.01$; in fact, to compare the different methods, we are only interested in observing how the number of non-empty sub-boxes changes depending on the bin width b_w . In general, the number of non-empty sub-boxes increases when b_w decreases and is upper bounded by the total number N of discrete samples; however, the upper bound is approached faster (and hence the number of non-empty sub-boxes is larger for the same b_w) when the space-filling index is higher, meaning that noise-induced corruption is larger.

Figure S6 shows the evolution of the space-filling index (number of non-empty sub-boxes) as a function of the bin width b_w resulting from applying the methodology described above to two different attractor reconstructions with different space-filling characteristic: the reconstruction with the Differentiator-based method (in blue) and the reconstruction with the Schreiber-Grassberger de-noising (in orange) in the presence of additive harmonic noise η_H .

For the time-delay embedding of the reconstructed attractor of the Lorenz system (S3), Figure 5 in the Main Manuscript shows the space-filling index (*i.e.*, number of non-empty sub-boxes) as a function of the bin width for the whole attractor, based on the noise-free signal data, the noisy measured signal data, the Differentiator-based reconstruction and the noisy reconstruction after Schreiber-Grassberger de-noising. Conversely, Figures S7 and S8 show the space-filling index of specific topological features of the attractor: its upper and lower holes, which are key properties often measured in terms of invariant features that one would want to persist in spite of the noise. The space-filling index is computed considering as regions of interest the square $[4.8, 11.75]^2$ for the upper hole and the square $[-11.46, -5.15]^2$ for the lower hole. For all noise types, the Differentiator yields a space-filling index that is almost identical, or very close, to that of the true attractor.

Figure S6: **Effectiveness of the space-filling index in quantifying the quality of attractor reconstruction: lower space-filling index corresponds to improved de-noising.** Top: space-filling index (*i.e.*, number of non-empty sub-boxes) as a function of the bin width, computed as described in Section S2.3, for the time-delay embedding of the reconstructed attractor of the Lorenz system (S3) obtained with the Differentiator-based method, having points with low space-filling index (blue), and obtained with the Schreiber-Grassberger de-noising, having points with high space filling index (orange). Bottom: related distribution of the non-empty sub-boxes in the time-delay coordinates for different values of bin width: a) $b_w = 0.01$; b) $b_w = 0.06$; c) $b_w = 0.016$; d) $b_w = 0.31$.

Figure S7: **For the upper hole of the Lorenz system, quantification through the space-filling index of the reconstruction quality, which is higher if the index value is closer to that obtained with noise-free data. In all simulated cases, the reconstruction based on the Differentiator outperforms the alternative approaches, both when the noise is additive and when the noise is multiplicative.** Space-filling index (*i.e.*, number of non-empty sub-boxes) as a function of the bin width, computed as described in Section S2.3, for the time-delay embedding of the reconstructed attractor of the Lorenz system (S3) focusing on its upper hole (considering as regions of interest the square $[4.8, 11.75]^2$, top panel). The index is computed for the noise-free signal data (blue), the noisy measured signal data (green), the Differentiator-based reconstruction, with Differentiator parameters as in Figure S4 (red) and the noisy reconstruction after Schreiber-Grassberger de-noising (violet). In the columns, we consider different types of noise corrupting the measured signal: Gaussian white noise η_1 ; Gaussian white noise η_2 ; Gaussian white noise η_3 ; harmonic noise η_H ; unbounded noise η_U . The noise is additive in the top row and multiplicative in the bottom row. The blue and red line often overlap, which attests to the high quality of the Differentiator-based attractor reconstruction; a larger space-filling index for a given bin width denotes poorer quality of the reconstruction. Multiplicative noises η_3 , η_H and η_U are so severe that most data points are scattered away from the rectangle bounding the upper hole, thus making the reconstruction based on noisy measured data (green) and the reconstruction after Schreiber-Grassberger de-noising (violet) appear less space-filling, even less than the true attractor (blue).

Figure S8: **For the lower hole of the Lorenz system, quantification through the space-filling index of the reconstruction quality, which is higher if the index value is closer to that obtained with noise-free data. In all simulated cases, the reconstruction based on the Differentiator outperforms the alternative approaches, both when the noise is additive and when the noise is multiplicative.** Space-filling index (*i.e.*, number of non-empty sub-boxes) as a function of the bin width, computed as described in Section S2.3, for the time-delay embedding of the reconstructed attractor of the Lorenz system (S3) focusing on its lower hole (considering as regions of interest the square $[-11.46, -5.15]^2$, bottom panel). The index is computed for the noise-free signal data (blue), the noisy measured signal data (green), the Differentiator-based reconstruction, with Differentiator parameters as in Figure S4 (red) and the noisy reconstruction after Schreiber-Grassberger de-noising (violet). In the columns, we consider different types of noise corrupting the measured signal: Gaussian white noise η_1 ; Gaussian white noise η_2 ; Gaussian white noise η_3 ; harmonic noise η_H ; unbounded noise η_U . The noise is additive in the top row and multiplicative in the bottom row. The blue and red line often overlap, which attests to the high quality of the Differentiator-based attractor reconstruction; a larger space-filling index for a given bin width denotes poorer quality of the reconstruction. Multiplicative noises η_3 , η_H and η_U are so severe that most data points are scattered away from the rectangle bounding the lower hole, thus making the reconstruction based on noisy measured data (green) and the reconstruction after Schreiber-Grassberger de-noising (violet) appear less space-filling, even less than the true attractor (blue).

S3 Hindmarsh-Rose model

The Hindmarsh-Rose model is given by the adimensionalised system [12]

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_1(t) = x_2(t) - ax_1^3(t) + bx_1^2(t) - x_3(t) + I \\ \dot{x}_2(t) = c - dx_1^2(t) - x_2(t) \\ \dot{x}_3(t) = r[s(x_1(t) - x_R) - x_3(t)] \end{cases} \quad (\text{S4})$$

(see the Main Manuscript for a complete description). We set the parameters as $a = 1$, $c = 1$, $d = 5$, $s = 4$, $x_R = -8/5$, $r = 0.01$, while we change the values of I and b so as to obtain five different regimes: quiescence ($I = 2.2$, $b = 3.2$), tonic spiking ($I = 2.5$, $b = 3$), square-wave bursting ($I = 3$, $b = 2.7$), plateau bursting ($I = 4$, $b = 2.5$) and chaotic bursting ($I = 2.7$, $b = 3.03$).

We simulate the system trajectory emanating from the initial condition $x(0) = [0.65 \ 0.55 \ 0.45]^\top$ for a total simulation time of 2,500 time units, but we remove the initial transient of 1,500 time units so as to let the trajectory converge to its attractor. Considering 10,000 time points per time unit, the simulation encompasses 10,000,001 time points.

We measure the clean (base) signal $\bar{y}(t) = x_3(t)$. Measurement noise $\eta(t)$ is introduced at each time step, as described in the Main Manuscript: the five noise types described in Section 2.4 of the Main Manuscript are injected so as to affect the measured signal both in an additive ($y(t) = \bar{y}(t) + \eta(t)$) and in a multiplicative ($y(t) = [1 + \eta(t)]\bar{y}(t)$) fashion. For each dynamic regime, this yields the ten different noisy signals shown in Figure S10 for quiescence, Figure S12 for tonic spiking, Figure S14 for square-wave bursting, Figure S16 for plateau bursting, Figure S18 for chaotic bursting. We first apply the Differentiator and then we remove the data corresponding to the first five units of time in order to obtain an output that does not contain the finite-time transient of the Differentiator [1]; see also Section S1.

The attractor reconstruction for each dynamic regime is performed with the same procedure described for the Lorenz system, according to the differential embedding procedure shown in Figure S9: the power of the Differentiator allows us to reconstruct the attractor in the original state space from measurements of a single variable (x_3), since it provides de-noised estimates of the signal and of its derivatives.

We set the Differentiator parameters as $n_d = 3$, $n_f = 9$, which results in

$$\lambda = (1.1, 65.22, 1890.6, 29064, 206531, 588869, 812652, 534837, 205679, 48747, 6944.8, 623.30, 32)$$

as per [3, Figure 1], and $L_0 = 10$. To implement the discrete L -adaptation of the Differentiator, we consider parameters $q = 0$ and $k_{\bar{\theta}} = 7 \cdot 10^{15}$ corresponding to the chosen λ as per [3, Table I]. The Differentiator outputs are shown in Figure S11 for the quiescence regime, Figure S13 for the tonic spiking regime, Figure S15 for the square-wave bursting regime, Figure S17 for the plateau bursting regime, Figure S19 for the chaotic bursting regime.

S3.1 Distribution of errors

Similarly to what was done for the Lorenz system, we quantify the error in attractor reconstruction by calculating the relative reconstruction errors $\tilde{E}_R(k)$ in the state-space coordinates as per Eq. (4) in the Main Manuscript, focusing on the Differentiator-based reconstruction. We compare the reconstruction error obtained with the Differentiator output and with the Differentiator output post-filtered using the SG filter to reduce chattering. Due to the interplay between fast and slow dynamics, more data points are simulated for the HR model so as to capture the characteristic features of all the considered dynamical regimes. Therefore, the Schreiber-Grassberger method is not tested since it becomes extremely demanding in terms of computational power and computational time complexity (for the Hindmarsh-Rose case-study, we have a two-orders-of-magnitude increase in the number of data points with respect to the case study with the Lorenz system).

The distributions of the errors are reported, for each noise type and for each regime of the HR model, in Figure S20 (for the case of additive noise) and Figure S21 (for the case of multiplicative noise); the

results are summarised in Tables S1, S2, S3, S4 and S5, for the five considered regimes. The obtained errors are worse than those obtained for the Lorenz system, since we use a single measured signal to reconstruct an attractor of a higher dimension, which requires the estimation of higher-order derivatives. In the additive noise case, the rigorous theoretical error bounds are known to become worse in this case; see Theorem 3. We use the SG filter with approximating polynomial of order two and approximation interval $M = 8251$ to reduce the error by attenuating chattering. We observe that the chaotic regime has errors of magnitude comparable to the other dynamical regimes, highlighting the fact that, for the quality of the Differentiator-based attractor reconstruction, the type of noise is more impactful than the nature of the dynamics; high intensities of stochastic noise make the reconstruction less precise, while deterministic noise types, even when unbounded, are better coped with.

The computational time complexity (on a Dell Inspiron 16 laptop with 16 GB RAM and 1.90 GHz Intel i5-1340P core processor running Windows), also reported in the tables, increases with respect to the case of the Lorenz system due to the larger number of data points used for the simulations, but remains in the range of seconds. The increase in computational time due to the post-filtering with the SG filter is only due to the Differentiator outputs that are strictly needed to reconstruct the attractor: in this case, we filter with the SG filter only up to the second order derivative, even though the Differentiator with $n_d = 3$ estimates also the third derivative (see Theorem 3).

\tilde{E}_R	Method	Additive noise					Multiplicative noise				
		η_1	η_2	η_3	η_H	η_U	η_1	η_2	η_3	η_H	η_U
Mean	Diff.	1.0	2.2	6.6	0.0031	1.3	1.8	4.6	21	0.0034	2.8
	Diff. SG	0.40	0.97	2.8	0.0011	0.72	0.76	2.0	8.1	0.0013	1.6
Median	Diff.	0.82	1.5	2.0	0.0012	0.90	1.3	1.9	3.7	0.0013	1.4
	Diff. SG.	0.33	0.76	1.5	$8.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.59	0.61	1.3	1.9	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.2
Max.	Diff.	15	56	260	0.32	320	29	220	960	0.35	1500
	Diff. SG.	3.3	10	52	0.12	18	6.6	43	330	0.14	100
T_{comp}	Diff. [s]	79	81	81	80	80	81	80	81	80	81
	Diff. SG [s]	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110

Table S1: **HR model, Quiescence: Reconstruction error and computational time achieved in numerical experiments show the efficiency and faithfulness of Differentiator-based attractor reconstruction. Top:** Summary statistics of relative errors $\tilde{E}_R(k)$, as per Eq. (4) in the Main Manuscript, for the reconstruction of the attractor from measurements subject to different noise types, using the Differentiator and the Differentiator with SG post-filtering. **Bottom:** Computational time T_{comp} for attractor reconstruction. The Differentiator parameters are $n_d = 3$, $n_f = 9$, $L_0 = 10$, $q = 0$, $k_{\bar{\theta}} = 7 \cdot 10^{15}$.

\tilde{E}_R	Method	Additive noise					Multiplicative noise				
		η_1	η_2	η_3	η_H	η_U	η_1	η_2	η_3	η_H	η_U
Mean	Diff.	0.98	2.1	6.4	0.0039	1.3	1.7	4.5	21	0.0043	2.7
	Diff. SG	0.38	0.92	2.7	0.0018	0.68	0.73	2.0	8.2	0.0021	1.6
Median	Diff.	0.76	1.4	1.9	0.0011	0.84	1.2	1.8	3.8	0.0012	1.3
	Diff. SG.	0.31	0.72	1.4	$8.3 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.56	0.57	1.2	1.9	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.2
Max.	Diff.	12	41	240	0.25	270	29	220	1400	0.27	880
	Diff. SG.	2.8	16	59	0.11	19	6.9	74	280	0.12	130
T_{comp}	Diff. [s]	80	80	80	79	81	82	81	80	80	80
	Diff. SG [s]	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110

Table S2: **HR model, Spiking: Reconstruction error and computational time achieved in numerical experiments show the efficiency and faithfulness of Differentiator-based attractor reconstruction. Top:** Summary statistics of relative errors $\tilde{E}_R(k)$, as per Eq. (4) in the Main Manuscript, for the reconstruction of the attractor from measurements subject to different noise types, using the Differentiator and the Differentiator with SG post-filtering. **Bottom:** Computational time T_{comp} for attractor reconstruction. The Differentiator parameters are $n_d = 3$, $n_f = 9$, $L_0 = 10$, $q = 0$, $k_{\bar{\theta}} = 7 \cdot 10^{15}$.

\tilde{E}_R	Method	Additive noise					Multiplicative noise				
		η_1	η_2	η_3	η_H	η_U	η_1	η_2	η_3	η_H	η_U
Mean	Diff.	0.83	1.8	5.7	0.0061	1.1	1.5	4.5	24	0.0068	2.7
	Diff. SG	0.33	0.79	2.3	0.0039	0.59	0.66	1.8	8.8	0.0045	1.5
Median	Diff.	0.62	1.1	1.7	0.0010	0.68	0.99	1.6	3.8	0.0011	1.1
	Diff. SG.	0.25	0.58	1.2	$8.4 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.45	0.47	1.1	1.8	$1.4 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.98
Max.	Diff.	12	40	180	0.14	430	31	220	1300	0.16	1800
	Diff. SG.	2.7	13	68	0.076	22	8.4	84	340	0.085	120
T_{comp}	Diff. [s]	79	79	78	77	78	79	80	80	79	81
	Diff. SG [s]	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110

Table S3: **HR model, Square-Wave bursting: Reconstruction error and computational time achieved in numerical experiments show the efficiency and faithfulness of Differentiator-based attractor reconstruction. Top:** Summary statistics of relative errors $\tilde{E}_R(k)$, as per Eq. (4) in the Main Manuscript, for the reconstruction of the attractor from measurements subject to different noise types, using the Differentiator and the Differentiator with SG post-filtering. **Bottom:** Computational time T_{comp} for attractor reconstruction. The Differentiator parameters are $n_d = 3$, $n_f = 9$, $L_0 = 10$, $q = 0$, $k_{\bar{\theta}} = 7 \cdot 10^{15}$.

\tilde{E}_R	Method	Additive noise					Multiplicative noise				
		η_1	η_2	η_3	η_H	η_U	η_1	η_2	η_3	η_H	η_U
Mean	Diff.	0.61	1.3	4.6	0.0057	0.79	1.5	5.7	42	0.0065	3.2
	Diff. SG	0.25	0.57	1.7	0.0040	0.43	0.62	2.1	16	0.0047	1.5
Median	Diff.	0.46	0.83	1.4	0.00097	0.48	0.86	1.5	5.8	0.0011	0.95
	Diff. SG.	0.19	0.42	0.91	$3.6 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.32	0.44	0.95	2.3	$5.1 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.87
Max.	Diff.	8.4	32	220	0.14	360	43	300	3100	0.16	2800
	Diff. SG.	2.0	12	49	0.073	14	7.9	69	1100	0.082	170
T_{comp}	Diff. [s]	79	80	80	80	80	82	80	79	82	80
	Diff. SG [s]	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110

Table S4: **HR model, Plateau bursting: Reconstruction error and computational time achieved in numerical experiments show the efficiency and faithfulness of Differentiator-based attractor reconstruction. Top:** Summary statistics of relative errors $\tilde{E}_R(k)$, as per Eq. (4) in the Main Manuscript, for the reconstruction of the attractor from measurements subject to different noise types, using the Differentiator and the Differentiator with SG post-filtering. **Bottom:** Computational time T_{comp} for attractor reconstruction. The Differentiator parameters are $n_d = 3$, $n_f = 9$, $L_0 = 10$, $q = 0$, $k_{\bar{\theta}} = 7 \cdot 10^{15}$.

Figure S9: **Block diagram of the attractor reconstruction procedure for the Hindmarsh-Rose system (S4) based on the Differentiator outputs.** The clean (base) measured signal $\bar{y} = x_3$ corrupted by the noise η yields the (noisy) measured signal y , which is then processed by the Differentiator to generate a de-noised estimate of y , y_D , and of its first and second derivatives, \dot{y}_D and \ddot{y}_D . Approximating x_3 as y_D , x_1 as a function of y_D and \dot{y}_D , and x_2 as a function of y_D , \dot{y}_D and \ddot{y}_D allows reconstruction of the system attractor in the original state-space coordinates x_1, x_2, x_3 .

\tilde{E}_R	Method	Additive noise					Multiplicative noise				
		η_1	η_2	η_3	η_H	η_U	η_1	η_2	η_3	η_H	η_U
Mean	Diff.	1.0	2.2	6.7	0.0039	1.3	1.9	5.3	27	0.0044	3.1
	Diff. SG	0.39	0.96	2.8	0.0018	0.70	0.82	2.3	10	0.0021	1.8
Median	Diff.	0.79	1.4	2.0	0.0012	0.87	1.3	1.9	4.7	0.0013	1.4
	Diff. SG.	0.32	0.74	1.5	$9.2 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0.58	0.64	1.4	2.1	$1.4 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.3
Max.	Diff.	12	41	270	0.26	200	31	200	1300	0.29	1100
	Diff. SG.	2.7	11	55	0.11	15	8.0	54	370	0.12	110
$T_{\text{comp}}[s]$	Diff.	80	80	80	79	80	80	79	80	79	80
	Diff. SG	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110	110

Table S5: **HR model, Chaotic spiking: Reconstruction error and computational time achieved in numerical experiments show the efficiency and faithfulness of Differentiator-based attractor reconstruction.** **Top:** Summary statistics of relative errors $\tilde{E}_R(k)$, as per Eq. (4) in the Main Manuscript, for the reconstruction of the attractor from measurements subject to different noise types, using the Differentiator and the Differentiator with SG post-filtering. **Bottom:** Computational time T_{comp} for attractor reconstruction. The Differentiator parameters are $n_d = 3$, $n_f = 9$, $L_0 = 10$, $q = 0$, $k_{\tilde{\theta}} = 7 \cdot 10^{15}$.

Figure S10: **Clean and noisy signals considered for the HR system in the quiescence regime.** Time series of the clean (base) measured signal $\bar{y} = x_3$ for the Hindmarsh-Rose system (S4) in the **quiescence** regime, in black, affected by additive (left) and multiplicative (right) noise to yield the measured signal y , in colour. From top to bottom, Gaussian noise $\eta_1(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.001)$ (blue), $\eta_2(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.01)$ (orange), $\eta_3(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.1)$ (violet); harmonic noise $\eta_H(t)$ as in Eq. (5) of the Main Manuscript (green); unbounded noise $\eta_U(t)$ as in Eq. (6) of the Main Manuscript (red). See Section 2.4 of the Main Manuscript for details about the different noise types.

Figure S11: **Differentiator output for the HR system in the quiescence regime: de-noised estimate of the measured signal and of its time derivatives.** Time series of the clean (base) measured signal $\bar{y} = x_3$ for the Hindmarsh-Rose system (S4) in the **quiescence** regime and of its derivatives $\dot{\bar{y}} = \dot{x}_3$ and $\ddot{\bar{y}} = \ddot{x}_3$, in blue, along with the corresponding signals y_D and \dot{y}_D , in red, reconstructed by the Differentiator with parameters $n_d = 3$, $n_f = 9$, $L_0 = 10$, $q = 0$, $k_{\bar{y}} = 7 \cdot 10^{15}$, in the presence of additive (left) and multiplicative (right) noise η_i , $i \in \{1, 2, 3, U, H\}$, as in Figure S10.

Figure S12: **Clean and noisy signals considered for the HR system in the spiking regime.** Time series of the clean (base) measured signal $\bar{y} = x_3$ for the Hindmarsh-Rose system (S4) in the **spiking** regime, in black, affected by additive (left) and multiplicative (right) noise to yield the measured signal y , in colour. From top to bottom, Gaussian noise $\eta_1(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.001)$ (blue), $\eta_2(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.01)$ (orange), $\eta_3(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.1)$ (violet); harmonic noise $\eta_H(t)$ as in Eq. (5) of the Main Manuscript (green); unbounded noise $\eta_U(t)$ as in Eq. (6) of the Main Manuscript (red). See Section 2.4 of the Main Manuscript for details about the different noise types.

Figure S13: **Differentiator output for the HR system in the spiking regime: de-noised estimate of the measured signal and of its time derivatives.** Time series of the clean (base) measured signal $\bar{y} = x_3$ for the Hindmarsh-Rose system (S4) in the **spiking** regime and of its derivatives $\dot{\bar{y}} = \dot{x}_3$ and $\ddot{\bar{y}} = \ddot{x}_3$, in blue, along with the corresponding signals y_D and \dot{y}_D , in red, reconstructed by the Differentiator with parameters $n_d = 3$, $n_f = 9$, $L_0 = 10$, $q = 0$, $k_{\bar{\theta}} = 7 \cdot 10^{15}$, in the presence of additive (left) and multiplicative (right) noise η_i , $i \in \{1, 2, 3, U, H\}$, as in Figure S12.

Figure S14: **Clean and noisy signals considered for the HR system in the square-wave bursting regime.** Time series of the clean (base) measured signal $\bar{y} = x_3$ for the Hindmarsh-Rose system (S4) in the **square-wave bursting** regime, in black, affected by additive (left) and multiplicative (right) noise to yield the measured signal y , in colour. From top to bottom, Gaussian noise $\eta_1(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.001)$ (blue), $\eta_2(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.01)$ (orange), $\eta_3(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.1)$ (violet); harmonic noise $\eta_H(t)$ as in Eq. (5) of the Main Manuscript (green); unbounded noise $\eta_U(t)$ as in Eq. (6) of the Main Manuscript (red). See Section 2.4 of the Main Manuscript for details about the different noise types.

Figure S15: **Differentiator output for the HR system in the square-wave bursting regime: de-noised estimate of the measured signal and of its time derivatives.** Time series of the clean (base) measured signal $\bar{y} = x_3$ for the Hindmarsh-Rose system (S4) in the **square-wave bursting** regime and of its derivatives $\dot{\bar{y}} = \dot{x}_3$ and $\ddot{\bar{y}} = \ddot{x}_3$, in blue, along with the corresponding signals y_D and \dot{y}_D , in red, reconstructed by the Differentiator with parameters $n_d = 3$, $n_f = 9$, $L_0 = 10$, $q = 0$, $k_{\bar{y}} = 7 \cdot 10^{15}$, in the presence of additive (left) and multiplicative (right) noise η_i , $i \in \{1, 2, 3, U, H\}$, as in Figure S14.

Figure S16: **Clean and noisy signals considered for the HR system in the plateau bursting regime.** Time series of the clean (base) measured signal $\bar{y} = x_3$ for the Hindmarsh-Rose system (S4) in the **plateau bursting** regime, in black, affected by additive (left) and multiplicative (right) noise to yield the measured signal y , in colour. From top to bottom, Gaussian noise $\eta_1(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.001)$ (blue), $\eta_2(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.01)$ (orange), $\eta_3(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.1)$ (violet); harmonic noise $\eta_H(t)$ as in Eq. (5) of the Main Manuscript (green); unbounded noise $\eta_U(t)$ as in Eq. (6) of the Main Manuscript (red). See Section 2.4 of the Main Manuscript for details about the different noise types.

Figure S17: **Differentiator output for the HR system in the plateau bursting regime: de-noised estimate of the measured signal and of its time derivatives.** Time series of the clean (base) measured signal $\bar{y} = x_3$ for the Hindmarsh-Rose system (S4) in the **plateau bursting** regime and of its derivatives $\dot{\bar{y}} = \dot{x}_3$ and $\ddot{\bar{y}} = \ddot{x}_3$, in blue, along with the corresponding signals y_D and \dot{y}_D , in red, reconstructed by the Differentiator with parameters $n_d = 3$, $n_f = 9$, $L_0 = 10$, $q = 0$, $k_{\bar{y}} = 7 \cdot 10^{15}$, in the presence of additive (left) and multiplicative (right) noise η_i , $i \in \{1, 2, 3, U, H\}$, as in Figure S16.

Figure S18: **Clean and noisy signals considered for the HR system in the chaotic bursting regime.** Time series of the clean (base) measured signal $\bar{y} = x_3$ for the Hindmarsh-Rose system (S4) in the **chaotic bursting** regime, in black, affected by additive (left) and multiplicative (right) noise to yield the measured signal y , in colour. From top to bottom, Gaussian noise $\eta_1(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.001)$ (blue), $\eta_2(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.01)$ (orange), $\eta_3(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.1)$ (violet); harmonic noise $\eta_H(t)$ as in Eq. (5) of the Main Manuscript (green); unbounded noise $\eta_U(t)$ as in Eq. (6) of the Main Manuscript (red). See Section 2.4 of the Main Manuscript for details about the different noise types.

Figure S19: **Differentiator output for the HR system in the chaotic bursting regime: de-noised estimate of the measured signal and of its time derivatives.** Time series of the clean (base) measured signal $\bar{y} = x_3$ for the Hindmarsh-Rose system (S4) in the **chaotic bursting** regime and of its derivatives $\dot{\bar{y}} = \dot{x}_3$ and $\ddot{\bar{y}} = \ddot{x}_3$, in blue, along with the corresponding signals y_D and \dot{y}_D , in red, reconstructed by the Differentiator with parameters $n_d = 3$, $n_f = 9$, $L_0 = 10$, $q = 0$, $k_{\bar{y}} = 7 \cdot 10^{15}$, in the presence of additive (left) and multiplicative (right) noise η_i , $i \in \{1, 2, 3, U, H\}$, as in Figure S18.

Figure S20: **HR system with additive noise: the distribution of reconstruction errors, along with average, median and worst-case errors, quantifies the faithfulness achieved by the Differentiator-based attractor reconstruction.** Distribution of relative reconstruction errors $\bar{E}_R(k)$, see Eq. (4) in the Main Manuscript, for the reconstruction of the attractor of the HR model, for the five considered dynamic regimes (in the rows) and the five considered **additive** noise types (columns), using the Differentiator (blue) and the Differentiator with SG post-filtering with parameter $M = 8251$ (green). The Differentiator parameters are $n_d = 3$, $n_f = 9$, $L_0 = 10$, $q = 0$, $k_{\bar{q}} = 7 \cdot 10^{15}$.

Figure S21: **HR system with multiplicative noise: the distribution of reconstruction errors, along with average, median and worst-case errors, quantifies the faithfulness achieved by the Differentiator-based attractor reconstruction.** Distribution of relative reconstruction errors $\tilde{E}_R(k)$, see Eq. (4) in the Main Manuscript, for the reconstruction of the attractor of the HR model, for the five considered dynamic regimes (in the rows) and the five considered **multiplicative** noise types (columns), using the Differentiator (blue) and the Differentiator with SG post-filtering with parameter $M = 8251$ (green). The Differentiator parameters are $n_d = 3$, $n_f = 9$, $L_0 = 10$, $q = 0$, $k_{\bar{\rho}} = 7 \cdot 10^{15}$.

S4 Epileptor model

We consider the Epileptor model given by [13]

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_1(t) = x_2(t) - f_1(x_1(t), x_4(t)) - x_3(t) + I_1 \\ \dot{x}_2(t) = r_2 - 5x_1^2(t) - x_2(t) \\ \dot{x}_3(t) = \frac{1}{\tau_0}[4(x_1(t) - r_1) - x_3(t)] \\ \dot{x}_4(t) = -x_5(t) + x_4(t) - x_4^3(t) + I_2 + 2u(t) - 0.3(x_3(t) - 3.5) \\ \dot{x}_5(t) = \frac{1}{\tau_2}[-x_5(t) + f_2(x_4(t))] \\ \dot{u}(t) = -\gamma[u(t) - 0.1x_1(t)] \end{cases} \quad (\text{S5})$$

with parameters $(r_1, r_2, I_1, I_2) = (-1.6, 1, 3.1, 0.45)$, time scale constants $(\tau_0, \tau_2, \gamma) = (2857, 10, 0.01)$, and coupling functions

$$\begin{aligned} f_1(x_1(t), x_4(t)) &= \begin{cases} x_1^3(t) - 3x_1^2(t), & x_1(t) < 0, \\ \{x_4(t) - 0.6[x_3(t) - 4]^2\}x_1(t), & x_1(t) \geq 0, \end{cases} \\ f_2(x_4(t)) &= \begin{cases} 0, & x_4(t) < -0.25, \\ 6[x_4(t) + 0.25], & x_4(t) \geq -0.25. \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S6})$$

See the Main Manuscript for a detailed description. With the chosen parameter values, the Epileptor model generates seizure-like events, as the time evolution of $x_1(t) + x_4(t)$ bears resemblance to experimentally recorded field potentials [13].

The Epileptor model generates seizure-like events when measuring $\bar{y}(t) = x_1(t) + x_4(t)$.

We simulate the system trajectory emanating from the initial condition

$$x(0) = [0.022 \ 0.91 \ 3.84 \ -1.11 \ 0.73 \ 0]^\top;$$

after removing the initial transient, the simulation encompasses 3,000,001 time points.

We measure three variables: x_1 , x_3 and x_4 . Measurement noise $\eta(t)$ is introduced at each time step, as described in the Main Manuscript: the five noise types described in Section 2.4 of the Main Manuscript are injected so as to affect the measured signal both in an additive ($y(t) = \bar{y}(t) + \eta(t)$) and in a multiplicative ($y(t) = [1 + \eta(t)]\bar{y}(t)$) fashion, thus yielding the ten different noisy signals shown in Figures S23 and S24. Measurements of each of the variables x_1 , x_3 and x_4 are assumed to be corrupted by the same noise.

Separately on each measured signal, we use the Differentiator with parameters $n_d = 2$, $n_f = 10$ (which results in the same λ and $k_{\bar{y}}$ as in Section S3), $L_0 = 50$ and $q = 0$. The de-noised signals produced by the Differentiator allows us to obtain a cleaner attractor in the $\{x_1, x_3, x_4\}$ space (see Figure 8 in the Main Manuscript). The Differentiator outputs are shown in Figure S25. Also, we then use the SG filter with order two approximating polynomial and approximation interval $M = 4551$ to reduce the error by attenuating chattering.

As done for the other models, we can assess the relative reconstruction errors \tilde{E}_R in attractor reconstruction (see Eq. (4) in the Main Manuscript), whose distribution is shown in Figure S22; the summary statistics for the errors obtained using the Differentiator and using the Differentiator with post-processing with the SG filter are summarised in Table S6. The results are similar to those obtained for the Lorenz system (see also the Main Manuscript for the summary table), while the computation time is longer due to the much higher number of sampling points. There is a significant decrease in the reconstruction error with respect to the HR model, even though the Epileptor model is more complex: this is due to the fact that, in this case, we are directly measuring the three variables x_1 , x_3 and x_4 to reconstruct the attractor in the $\{x_1, x_3, x_4\}$ sub-space, and therefore the Differentiator is only used to estimate the zeroth-order derivatives, leading to a more accurately de-noised output (for the rigorous error bounds in the case of additive noise, see Theorem 3).

Figure S22: **Epileptor system: the distribution of reconstruction errors, along with average, median and worst-case errors, quantifies the faithfulness achieved by the Differentiator-based attractor reconstruction.** Distribution of relative errors $\tilde{E}_R(k)$, see Eq. (4) in the Main Manuscript, for the reconstruction of the attractor of the Epileptor model (S5), for both additive and multiplicative noise, using the Differentiator (blue) and the Differentiator with SG post-filtering with parameter $M = 4551$ (green). The Differentiator parameters are $n_d = 2$, $n_f = 10$, $L_0 = 50$, $q = 0$, $k_{\bar{\theta}} = 7 \cdot 10^{15}$.

\tilde{E}_R	Method	Additive noise					Multiplicative noise				
		η_1	η_2	η_3	η_H	η_U	η_1	η_2	η_3	η_H	η_U
Mean	Diff.	0.012	0.017	0.034	0.01	0.012	0.015	0.027	0.067	0.010	0.014
	Diff. SG	0.0082	0.0098	0.015	0.0075	0.0083	0.0092	0.013	0.025	0.0075	0.0094
Median	Diff.	0.0031	0.0093	0.027	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-8}$	0.0018	0.0069	0.020	0.057	$2.4 \cdot 10^{-8}$	0.0041
	Diff. SG.	0.0011	0.0033	0.0093	$3.2 \cdot 10^{-9}$	0.0012	0.0024	0.0073	0.020	$3.2 \cdot 10^{-9}$	0.0027
Max.	Diff.	0.37	0.36	0.39	0.37	0.37	0.37	0.38	0.38	0.37	0.37
	Diff. SG.	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.22
$T_{\text{comp}} [s]$	Diff.	66	66	65	67	66	66	67	65	65	66
	Diff. SG	70	69	69	70	69	69	70	69	69	69

Table S6: **Epileptor model (S5): Reconstruction error and computational time achieved in numerical experiments show the efficiency and faithfulness of Differentiator-based attractor reconstruction.** **Top:** Summary statistics of relative errors $\tilde{E}_R(k)$, as per Eq. (4) in the Main Manuscript, for the reconstruction of the attractor from measurements subject to different noise types, using the Differentiator and the Differentiator with SG post-filtering. **Bottom:** Computational time T_{comp} for attractor reconstruction. The Differentiator parameters are $n_d = 2$, $n_f = 10$, $L_0 = 50$, $q = 0$, $k_{\bar{\theta}} = 7 \cdot 10^{15}$.

In addition, we consider reconstruction of the Epileptor attractor from a different measured signal. In particular, we assume to measure the signal $\bar{y}(t) = x_1(t) + x_4(t)$, subject to noise, and we apply the Differentiator – with the same parameters as in the previous analysis – to provide an estimate of the signal and of its first derivative, which we use to reconstruct the system trajectory in the $\{\bar{y}, \dot{\bar{y}}\}$ space after post-processing the Differentiator output with a SG filter with approximating polynomial of order $m = 2$ and approximation interval $M = 2751$. The obtained results are shown in Figure S26, along with a comparison with the true signal, its true derivative and the resulting true trajectory in the $\{\bar{y}, \dot{\bar{y}}\}$ space.

Figure S23: **Clean and noisy signals considered for the Epileptor system with additive noise.** Time series of the clean (base) measured signals x_1 , x_4 and x_3 for the Epileptor model (S5), in black, affected by **additive** noise to yield the measured signals, in colour. From top to bottom, Gaussian noise $\eta_1(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.01)$ (blue), $\eta_2(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.1)$ (orange), $\eta_3(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ (violet); harmonic noise $\eta_H(t)$ as in Eq. (5) of the Main Manuscript (green); unbounded noise $\eta_U(t)$ as in Eq. (6) of the Main Manuscript (red). See Section 2.4 of the Main Manuscript for details about the different noise types.

Figure S24: **Clean and noisy signals considered for the Epileptor system with multiplicative noise.** Time series of the clean (base) measured signals x_1 , x_4 and x_3 for the Epileptor model (S5), in black, affected by **multiplicative** noise to yield the measured signals, in colour. From top to bottom, Gaussian noise $\eta_1(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.01)$ (blue), $\eta_2(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.1)$ (orange), $\eta_3(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ (violet); harmonic noise $\eta_H(t)$ as in Eq. (5) of the Main Manuscript (green); unbounded noise $\eta_U(t)$ as in Eq. (6) of the Main Manuscript (red). See Section 2.4 of the Main Manuscript for details about the different noise types.

Figure S25: **Differentiator output for the Epileptor system: de-noised estimate of the measured signals.** Time series of the clean (base) measured signals x_1 , x_4 and x_3 for the Epileptor model (S5), in blue, along with the corresponding signals, in red, reconstructed by the Differentiator with parameters $n_d = 2$, $n_f = 10$, $L_0 = 50$, $q = 0$, $k_{\bar{\theta}} = 7 \cdot 10^{15}$, in the presence of additive (left) and multiplicative (right) noise η_i , $i \in \{1, 2, 3, U, H\}$, as in Figure S23 and Figure S24.

Figure S26: **The Differentiator enables de-noising and faithful attractor reconstruction for the Epileptor system affected by various types of additive and multiplicative noise, in the $\{\bar{y}, \dot{\bar{y}}\}$ space.** Reconstruction of the trajectories of the Epileptor (S5) in the $\{\bar{y}, \dot{\bar{y}}\}$ space, where $\bar{y}(t) = x_1(t) + x_4(t)$, in the presence of additive and multiplicative noise. The Differentiator output is post-processed with a SG filter with approximating polynomial of order two and $M = 2751$. **Top panel:** noise-free signals \bar{y} and $\dot{\bar{y}}$, along with the true trajectory of the system (black) in the $\{\bar{y}, \dot{\bar{y}}\}$ space. **Top:** for the case of additive (upper row) and of multiplicative (lower row) noise, reconstruction of the attractor in the $\{\bar{y}, \dot{\bar{y}}\}$ space from measurements corrupted by Gaussian noise $\eta_1(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.01)$ (blue), $\eta_2(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 0.1)$ (orange), $\eta_3(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ (violet); harmonic noise $\eta_H(t)$ as in Eq. (5) of the Main Manuscript (green); unbounded noise $\eta_U(t)$ as in Eq. (6) of the Main Manuscript (red). See Section 2.4 of the Main Manuscript for details about the different noise types. The Differentiator parameters are $n_d = 2$, $n_f = 10$, $L_0 = 50$, $q = 0$, $k_{\bar{\theta}} = 7 \cdot 10^{15}$.

S5 Empirical data: reconstruction of unknown attractors

We test the Differentiator on an empirical dataset of Local Field Potential (LFP) recordings, obtained from measurements of the brain activity of Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) larvae from the genetic strain KCNQ5 LoF model *kcnq5a^{sa9563}* (see the Main Manuscript for more information on accessibility, handling, ethical statements and husbandry). Figure S27 contains the measured time series, the Differentiator outputs, and the three-dimensional Takens embeddings of the labelled and segmented events (Background and Seizure, with sampling at 2,000 Hz) that complement Figure 10 in the Main Manuscript. The time delay is computed according to insights and considerations present in [9], leading to the choice of τ reported in each figure panel.

For seizure events, the Differentiator highlights a clear structure that evolves as a semi-loop and suggests some form of pattern or coherence. Background events are characterised by an agglomerate of points that, except for punctual and sparse spikes, are akin to typical attractors of semi-random signals. An exception is constituted by data segment A5: differently from all the other data segments of the Background type, the trajectory in the Takens embedding of data segment A5 shows a semi-loop that is similar to those present in the data segments of the Seizure type. This suggests that segment A5 may contain the beginning of a seizure event, perhaps because the corresponding time series has been truncated too late; it may be worth analysing more deeply the labelling procedure of that specific time series.

Figure S27: **The Differentiator enables signal de-noising and attractor reconstruction from segmented Local Field Potential empirical recordings of the brain activity of Zebrafish larvae, and reveals distinct key topological structures: central bulks in segments labelled as Background activity (with the exception of case A5, which may have been mislabelled) and semi-loops in segments labelled as Seizure events.** Local Field Potential recordings at 2,000 Hz of the brain activity of Zebrafish larvae (blue) and the corresponding de-noised signal provided by the Differentiator with parameters $n_d = 3$, $n_f = 9$, $L_0 = 750$, $k_{\bar{\theta}} = 7 \cdot 10^{15}$ and $q = 0$ (orange), and the corresponding three-dimensional Takens embedding (with time-delay as in the lower right corner of each panel) for data segments labelled as Background (left) and as Seizure (right).

References

- [1] A. Levant, M. Livne, Robust exact filtering differentiators, *European Journal of Control* 55 (2020) 33–44.
- [2] A. Levant, Higher-order sliding modes, differentiation and output-feedback control, *International journal of Control* 76 (9-10) (2003) 924–941.
- [3] A. Hanan, A. Levant, A. Jbara, Low-chattering discretization of homogeneous differentiators, *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control* 67 (6) (2021) 2946–2956.
- [4] A. Levant, M. Livne, X. Yu, Sliding-mode-based differentiation and its application, *IFAC-PapersOnLine* 50 (1) (2017) 1699–1704.
- [5] E. N. Lorenz, Deterministic nonperiodic flow, *Journal of Atmospheric Sciences* 20 (2) (1963) 130 – 141.
- [6] A. N. Montanari, L. Freitas, D. Proverbio, J. Gonçalves, Functional observability and subspace reconstruction in nonlinear systems, *Physical Review Research* 4 (4) (2022) 043195.
- [7] T. Schreiber, P. Grassberger, A simple noise-reduction method for real data, *Physics Letters A* 160 (5) (1991) 411–418.
- [8] P. Grassberger, R. Hegger, H. Kantz, C. Schaffrath, T. Schreiber, On noise reduction methods for chaotic data, *Chaos: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Nonlinear Science* 3 (2) (1993) 127–141.
- [9] T. Buzug, G. Pfister, Optimal delay time and embedding dimension for delay-time coordinates by analysis of the global static and local dynamical behavior of strange attractors, *Physical review A* 45 (10) (1992) 7073.
- [10] R. W. Schafer, What is a Savitzky-Golay filter?, *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine* 28 (4) (2011) 111–117.
- [11] J. Wu, X. Jin, S. Mi, J. Tang, An effective method to compute the box-counting dimension based on the mathematical definition and intervals, *Results in Engineering* 6 (2020) 100106.
- [12] J. L. Hindmarsh, R. Rose, A model of neuronal bursting using three coupled first order differential equations, *Proceedings of the Royal society of London. Series B. Biological sciences* 221 (1222) (1984) 87–102.
- [13] V. K. Jirsa, W. C. Stacey, P. P. Quilichini, A. I. Ivanov, C. Bernard, On the nature of seizure dynamics, *Brain* 137 (8) (2014) 2210–2230.